

UNIQUE METHODS OF USING LOCAL SOURCES
RELATED TO WORLD WAR II IN HISTORY CLASSES
IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT. The teaching of local history in schools as the part of the history curriculum has been advocated since the beginning of the twentieth century. Local history has been recommended as an active way of history learning in some countries. Local history has become popular again with debates on globalisation and postmodernism in recent years. The importance of local history is emphasised in the new Social Knowledge and History Curriculum in Uzbekistan. The aim of this article is discuss the place and purpose of local history in history education. It will review relevant literature to elicit the potential benefits and problems of using local history in schools. Some suggestions to use local history during history lessons more effectively also will be given.

Keywords: Teaching history, history education, local history, teaching local history.

The Soviet government set out to reshape dramatically the society in Uzbekistan and they needed an educational system to facilitate this change. They changed the education system from one of backward, religious institutions to a secular system built upon Marxist/Leninist ideology within two decades. The system they built, designed to eradicate illiteracy and facilitate social engineering, was geared towards creating a homogeneous Soviet citizen. While the Soviet education system had achieved impressive results, even by international standards, the higher education system in Uzbekistan had to be reformed fundamentally again after independence in order to enable it to meet the demands of an emerging market economy with a rapidly increasing population. The

Uzbek government has already carried out a comprehensive overhaul of the entire education system and continues to provide relatively high levels of funding for the sector. The purpose of the paper is to evaluate the changes which the Uzbek higher educational system has experienced since the times of the khanates and to offer constructive policy recommendations for further improvement. After this short introductory section, Section 2 and Section 3 describe the Uzbek education system before and after the October revolution respectively. Section 4, discusses the nature of reforms that have been carried out in the education sector of the country since independence, focusing particularly on the higher education sector reforms. Finally, Section 5, discusses some

4 possible limitations of the present system and offers suggestions for further strengthening the system. 2. The Central Asian Education System before the Soviet Reforms The Soviet academics/authorities maintained the view, which became the conventional wisdom for sovietologists worldwide, that before the Bolshevik revolution, the education system in Central Asia was extremely backward with an estimated adult literacy rate of as low as 2% (Grenoble 2003).¹ However, more recent and detailed studies, based on information that became available only after the collapse of the Soviet Union, reveal that the pre-Soviet education system was more robust and had its own merits, which had been ignored by the Soviet writers. It had been, for many centuries, a tradition of Central Asian kings and princes to take great pride in the size of their libraries and the entourage of prominent scholars and poets in their courts. They extended their generous patronage to the brightest literary and scientific minds of their time and provided educational institutions with landed estates which were used to fund schools (maktab) and colleges (madrasa). Maktabas were the starting points where pupils would learn reading, writing, and other basic life skills. The more talented of the pupils would move onto madrasas for further education where they would spend over 10 years studying theology, literature, law, philosophy, and other 'worldly wisdom'. The curriculum was heavily based on

Islamic teachings, as the Shariah was the Law of the Land. The noteworthy feature of the system was that both maktabas and madrasas were free for the general public, funded by the landed estates and charitable donations, which included gifts from the parents of their pupils. Towards the end of the nineteenth century, the number of madrasas in the Bukharan emirate alone, with a population of around 5 million, had been estimated to be about 180 (103 of them in the 1st capital city of Bukhara) with some 15,000 students. At the same time 1,800 Maktabas taught another 150,000 pupils, while Khiva, Tashkent, Samarkand, Sir Darya, and Khokand had 25, 10, 50, 21, and 118 Madrasas respectively (Allworth 1994; Skrine and Ross 1899). Given that these institutions helped to add to the stock of literate adults continuously over time, the conventional wisdom of the Soviet writers, mentioned above, seems to be a gross underestimate of the real picture. Teachings at Madrasas were based on the seminar/tutorial system and successful graduates would develop into all-round intellectuals, as described below by Allworth (1994: 349): ‘A diligent, capable scholar emerged with the command of the Central Asian Turkic, as well as Persian and Arabic literary languages and a thorough grounding in the great writings of the poets, theologians, philosophers, historians, and geographers of the Muslim world, plus long experience with the pedagogical methods employed in the maktaband madrasah. ... The talented Central Asian composed and performed original music, wrote elegant poetry employing a fine calligraphy, disputed religious questions with learned theologians, and actively participated in the witty, intellectual circles found in every important center.’ The graduates would then expect to become employed as ‘a teacher or professor, a secretary to merchants, nobility, or other men of affairs, manager of a philanthropic institution, a judge or law clerk, or as a last resort a member of clergy’ (ibid: 354). In other words, whatever profession they chose, they would become leading intellectuals in

the community. In short, although the education system of this period was not free from problems, through maktab and madrasas funded by the landed estates, it provided the general public with reasonable opportunities for free education and in this sense satisfied at least the minimum need of a feudalistic society for intellectual minds. The system provided talented individuals with an opportunity to achieve their potential and offered them the limited upward social mobility afforded by an otherwise rigid feudal society. The society was rigid in the sense that, it protected the privileges of the royal and upper class families and the best the ordinary people could hope for were clerical positions at royal courts.

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6 similar government related offices. However, although the education system of this period had appropriate structures and institutions that met the requirements of a feudalistic society, which had already become past history in the more advanced Western capitalist countries, it was outdated and suffered from a number of weaknesses. First, the quality of education was not uniform throughout all educational institutions and furthermore the majority of the population did not even attain an education good enough to enable them to read and write. Only a handful of madrasas in big cities such as Mir-Arab in Bukhara and Beklarbegi in Tashkent could boast of the kind of quality described by Allworth. Secondly, even the top institutions were far behind their European counterparts, especially in terms teaching science subjects such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, engineering, etc. A group of local intellectuals, inspired by the Muslim enlightenment movements in European Russia, initiated a reform movement which later became known as Jadidism.² The Jadids, as the movement members were called, actively promoted reforms in the methodology of teaching and the ways it was organized and administered at local Maktab and Madrasas. They also published new text books and introduced new subjects to be taught in these institutions. As most of the members of the reform movement were from wealthy merchant families, they had travelled around the world, were aware of the progress made in the Western world

and were particularly inspired by the works of the 'Young Turks' movement in Turkey. The Jadids also set up a foundation that sponsored talented youth who wanted to continue their studies abroad, mainly in Germany. Unfortunately, the reform movement in Central Asia faced a formidable opposition from such traditionalists as the members of the clergy. The clergy were able to stifle most of the proposed reforms because of their direct involvement in the administration of maktabas and madrasas. As a result.

Surprisingly, at least in the earlier years of the Bolshevik revolution, the Jadids found more support for their cause from the new Soviet government and took high ranking positions in the first Communist administration in Central Asia. However, that co-operation did not last very long, because the Jadid ideology contradicted the Soviet plans for turning Central Asians into homogeneous Soviet citizens or 'HomoSovieticus', who would speak the same language (Russian) and share the same Marxist-atheist culture. The essence of the conflict, also common in other parts of the Soviet Union at the time and termed the 'Red Expert problem' in the literature, was that, although the Communist Party held political power in key areas of social and economic life, at the grassroots levels they had to rely too much on the indigenous experts and managers, who did not necessarily share the communist vision and ideology; and in fact more often than not resisted reforms introduced by the Communists. By the 1930s the Communist Party apparatus had completed the 'liberation' of the country from the hands of the non-Party specialists and replaced them by a newly created class of 'Red-experts', who by now had acquired adequate technical training and skills to deal with the issues of the economy themselves (Guroff 1983: 202). In reality, the Communists went a step further in their pursuit of solving the 'Red Expert' problem, as they purged everyone with the slightest perceived connection with the previous regime. Unfortunately, the purges swept away not only the Jadid reforms but also the personalities associated with the Jadid movement; as most of these pioneers of

the early educational reform either had to leave the country or were executed before the end of the 1930s.

All in all, in addition to returns to education, one of the main reasons why the brightest candidates are opting out of science and engineering-related programmes is the Uzbek society's perception about security of employment. Since the state was the sole provider of secure employment in all sectors of the economy during the Soviet period, the society has become used to associating job security with employment in the public sector. Since independence, such sectors as agriculture and manufacturing have been privatized or are in the process of being gradually privatized. As a result, 'secure' employment can be found either in state administrative departments or in state-owned institutions such as banks. This could explain the overwhelming preference for training in administrative, diplomatic and legal skills on the part of the brightest minds in the society. Obviously, as the market economy matures and people's faith in the resilience of the private sector grows, this tendency will gradually change. However, the policy makers may consider looking into ways of encouraging bright students to train for skills which can help accelerate and strengthen the growth of the productive sectors of the economy. The fact remains that the brightest candidates opt for programmes which prepare them more for employment in the bureaucracy or service sector.

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